

Bibliometric Analysis on Socio Pragmatics Study by Using Scopus Database

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Abstract: The purpose of this research is to analyze the comprehensive literature and to examine the research trend of today in all over the world or in the future especially on Sociopragmatics study. There are some specific aims of this research, namely to do the mapping analysis in order to identify the publication year and geographic distribution, source, citation and keyword of publication as well as co-occurrent on Sociopragmatics study, to summarize the research topic on Sociopragmatics study, to determine the research gap and to determine the future road map of the research on Sociopragmatics study. The data of this study were taken from Scopus database. Scopus is a database of international journal which has very good reputation all over the world and it has very tight turnitin system, so that the articles that are published in this Scopus indexed journal will have very good quality. There are so many articles discuss about linguistics published in the Scopus journal, one of them concerns on Sociopragmatics study. Data in this research is Sociopragmatics study taken from Scopus database on the 15th of February 2022. The problems discussed in this paper are: The development of publication from year to year, the most used keyword, the most cited citation, the most publication country.

Keywords: Sociopragmatics, Scopus, Database

I. INTRODUCTION

Scopus is a database of international journal which has very good reputation all over the world and it has very tight turnitin system, so that the articles that are published in this Scopus indexed journal will have very good quality. There are so many articles discuss about linguistics published in the Scopus journal, one of them concerns on sociopragmatics study. Data in this research is sociopragmatics study taken from Scopus database on the 15th of February 2022. The problems discussed in this paper are: The development of publication from year to year, the most used keyword, the most cited citation, the most publication country.

The purpose of this research is to analyze the comprehensive literature and to examine the research trend of today in all over the world or in the future especially on sociopragmatics study. There are some specific aims of this research, namely to do the mapping analysis in order to identify the publication year and geographic distribution, source, citation and keyword of publication as well as co-occurrent on sociopragmatics study, to summarize the research topic on sociopragmatics study, to determine the research gap and to determine the future road map of the research on sociopragmatics study.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

The data in this study was taken from Scopus database by using VOSviewer and Tableau Software. Vosviewer is a tool that is used to construct and visualizing bibliometric networks. There were some visual data were taken from Vosviewer namely the development of publication, the most used keyword data, the most citation data, the most cited journal data, and the most publication country. The analysis can be seen as follows.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This subchapter discusses about sociopragmatics study in terms of some points namely the development of publication, the most used keyword data, the most citation data, the most cited journal data, and the most publication country.

Data I

Chart Development of publication from year to year (the data was taken from Software Vosviewer)

Chart I

Chart II

Based on the data above, there was only few research on sociopragmatics study in 1984, 1987, and we could see there was development on sociopragmatics research in 1992. the significant increase happened on sociopragmatics study in 2003, however in 2005 it was decreased. Meanwhile, in 2011 the significant increase occurred again. The number of research on linguistics study seemed to be increased again in 2015 and 2019. However, it was decreased after 2019, it could predict that in 2019 the covid 19 pandemic became the reason for this case, so that in 2021, there was significant decrease for this research publication.

Having seen the data, we could see there was fluctuation number of sociopragmatic study from year to year. There were increase numbers of research on Sociopragmatics study in 2003, 2011, 2015, 2019. Meanwhile, there were decrease numbers of Socio pragmatics study in 2005, 2009, 2013, 2017, there was significant decrease for this research publication in 2021.

Data II

Keywords data could help us to see the interrelation among the particular study with the other cluster. In this case we can see the interrelation among the sociopragmatics study with the other cluster.

The meaning of the colour showed interrelation among the clusters or the topics, meanwhile the size of the ball showed the frequency of the keyword appearance. For instance, the size of the ball was as the core and showed the prominent appearance.

It could be seen that the sociopragmatics was marked by the biggest blue ball, it has interrelation with speech act analysis such as locution, illocution and perlocution, context of situation (time, place and participant). The object of the research can be taken from facebook, twitter (it can be seen on the top of the chart, namely the small balls)

Chart II

It could be seen that sociopragmatics research (which was marked by blue big ball on the chart) this research was closely related with the analysis of bilingualism, code switching. The objects of the research can be taken from the social media (as we can see the small balls on the top chart).

Data III

Data the most cited citation or the famous author which is mostly used in the data base scopus on Sociopragmatics study

Based on the data, there are 12 clusters with variant colours. Having seen from the data, the green ball stated Janet Holmes as the most cited author for Sociopragmatics study. It can be proved from the ball with the biggest size.

Data IV

Data about the most publication country. The Data base Scopus was taken from Vosviewer Software.

The Data above shows the interrelation among the countries that published the sociopragmatics research. America produced sociopragmatics research in 2012. In 2016, there were some countries produced the sociopragmatics research namely Spain and Turkey. Meanwhile Germany, France and Australia published research on Sociopragmatics study in 2014. Moreover, Poland, Scotland and China published this research in 2018.

Data V

The most cited journal on Sociopragmatics study.

The data showed the most cited journal on sociopragmatics research was *Journal of Pragmatics*, moreover the journal that gave significant contribution toward sociopragmatics research namely *journal of historical*

pragmatics, pragmatics and society language and science.

IV. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Scopus is a database of international journals that are recognized all over the world with a strict turnitin system, so that articles published in Scopus indexed journals have reliable quality. There are many articles that concern on linguistics that have been published in Scopus indexed journals, one of them is sociopragmatics. The data in this paper was taken from the Scopus data base on February 15, 2022 focused on sociopragmatics. There are some interesting things to discuss in this paper, namely the development of publication from year to year, the most used keyword, the most cited citation, the most publication country. The main of this study were to conduct a comprehensive literature review and to examine current and future worldwide research trends of sociopragmatics. The conclusion that can be drawn from this research is that bibliometric analysis is very interesting and important to do, in order to know the development of science and research in various countries by taking the Scopus data base through VOSviewer software. In addition, we can also find out the countries that have the highest publications, the most widely used theories, so that we can increase our knowledge about the development of world research with specific studies. Suggestions for other researchers can use the VOSviewer software to perform specific bibliometric analysis of other branches of science according to the fields of expertise and interest.

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